

Chemistry of Thorium. Part I. Amino Derivatives of Thorium (IV) Chloride

Sarju Prasad and Suresh Kumar

The amino derivatives of thorium (IV) chloride have been prepared by the action of ThCl_4 on some aromatic primary (mono- and di-) amines; their properties have been studied and structures discussed.

Matthews (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1898, **24**, 815) obtained a number of amino derivatives of thorium chloride by the action of ThCl_4 on ammonia and respective bases in ether and also those of ThBr_4 by the action of solid ThBr_4 on gaseous ammonia and the respective amine.

Chauvenet (*Compt. rend.*, 1911, **151**, 387) studied the action of ThCl_4 on liquid and gaseous ammonia and reported the formation of a number of ammines which gave $\text{Th}(\text{NH}_2)_4$ at 250-300° and $\text{Th}(\text{NH})_2$ at red heat.

Brintzinger and Hesse (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1944, **252**, 293) reported formation of a number of co-ordination compounds of ThCl_4 on some aliphatic amines.

Fowles and Pollard (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 4128) obtained the hexammine, $\text{ThCl}_4 \cdot 6\text{NH}_3$, by the action of NH_3 on ThCl_4 at -36°.

No systemic work appears to have been done on the reactions of ThCl_4 with aromatic amines. The present investigation was therefore undertaken with a view to studying the formation of compounds of thorium tetrachloride with aromatic primary mono- and diamines in anhydrous ether.

EXPERIMENTAL

Anhydrous thorium (IV) chloride was prepared by the method of Dean and Chandler (*Nuclear Sci. & Eng.*, 1957, **2**, 57), extracted with anhydrous ether (distilled over sodium metal), and analysed for purity. The amines and other chemicals used were of B. D. H. (A. R.) or E. Merck's E. P. quality.

In all the cases moderately dilute ethereal solution of amine was slowly added to the ethereal solution of ThCl_4 with constant shaking till complete precipitation. It was allowed to stand for an hour in a desiccator, filtered, and washed with ether till free of the reactants. The precipitate was dried over fused calcium chloride in a vacuum desiccator at the room temperature and analysed.

Thorium was estimated as ThO_2 by charring a weighed quantity of the compound with H_2SO_4 (conc.) followed by oxidation of the organic matter with HNO_3 (conc.) and subsequently precipitating $\text{Th}(\text{OH})_4$ by an excess of NH_4OH . The precipitate was filtered, washed

TABLE I
Compounds of thorium (IV) chloride with aromatic primary monoamines.

No.	Amines.	Temp.	%Thorium.		%Chlorine.		%Nitrogen.		Probable formulae.
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	
1.	Benzylamine	M.p.	28.48	28.94	17.56	17.70	6.87	6.98	[Th(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ NH ₂) ₄]Cl ₄
2.	<i>o</i> -Toluidine	"	28.56	28.94	17.76	17.70	6.73	6.93	[Th(C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃)NH ₂) ₄]Cl ₄
3.	<i>p</i> -Toluidine	Decomp.	28.63	28.94	17.53	17.70	6.89	6.93	[Th(C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃)NH ₂) ₄]Cl ₄
4.	<i>m</i> -Toluidine	"	28.73	28.94	17.46	17.70	6.74	6.98	[Th(C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃)NH ₂) ₄]Cl ₄
5.	<i>o</i> -Anisidine	"	26.89	26.70	16.13	16.39	6.23	6.46	[Th(CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ NH ₂) ₄]Cl ₄
6.	<i>p</i> -Anisidine	"	26.52	26.70	16.27	16.39	6.29	6.46	[Th(CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ NH ₂) ₄]Cl ₄
7.	<i>m</i> -Anisidine	"	26.47	26.70	13.03	16.39	6.18	6.46	[Th(CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ NH ₂) ₄]Cl ₄
8.	<i>o</i> -Phenetidine	"	24.78	25.17	14.90	15.39	5.84	6.07	[Th(C ₂ H ₅ OC ₆ H ₄ NH ₂) ₄]Cl ₄
9.	<i>p</i> -Phenetidine	"	24.95	25.17	14.88	15.39	5.76	6.07	[Th(C ₂ H ₅ OC ₆ H ₄ NH ₂) ₄]Cl ₄
10.	α -Naphthylamine	"	24.09	24.53	14.64	15.08	5.58	5.92	[Th(C ₁₀ H ₇ NH ₂) ₄]Cl ₄
11.	β -Naphthylamine	"	24.67	24.53	14.76	15.08	5.64	5.92	[Th(C ₁₀ H ₇ NH ₂) ₄]Cl ₄

TABLE II
Compounds of thorium (IV) chloride with aromatic primary diamines.

No.	Diamines.	Temp.	%Thorium.		%Chlorine.		%Nitrogen.		Probable formulae.
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	
1.	<i>o</i> -Phenylenediamine	Decomp.	39.59	39.33	23.74	24.06	9.21	9.48	[Th(H ₂ NC ₆ H ₄ NH ₂) ₂]Cl ₄
2.	<i>p</i> -Phenylenediamine	"	38.87	39.33	23.65	24.06	9.12	9.48	[Th(H ₂ NC ₆ H ₄ NH ₂) ₂]Cl ₄
3.	<i>m</i> -Phenylenediamine	"	36.91	39.33	24.37	24.06	9.07	9.48	[Th(H ₂ NC ₆ H ₄ NH ₂) ₂]Cl ₄
4.	Phenylenediamine	"	28.38	28.70	17.08	17.61	6.53	6.94	[Th(C ₆ H ₃ NHNH ₂) ₄]Cl ₄
5.	Benzidine	"	31.56	31.27	18.80	19.13	7.19	7.54	[Th(H ₂ NC ₆ H ₄ C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂) ₂]Cl ₄
6.	<i>o</i> -Dianisidine.	"	26.43	26.92	16.23	16.47	6.03	6.49	[Th(CH ₃ O.NH ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ C ₆ H ₃) ₂]Cl ₄
7.	<i>o</i> -Tolidine	"	28.56	29.08	17.36	17.70	6.71	7.02	[Th(CH ₃ .NH ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ C ₆ H ₃ NH ₂ .CH ₃) ₂]Cl ₄

thoroughly, dried, ignited to ThO_2 , and weighed. Chlorine was estimated by Piria and Schiff's method as AgCl and nitrogen by Kjeldahl's method.

General Properties.—All the compounds are coloured, amorphous, insoluble in ether, CCl_4 , CHCl_3 , and benzene but sparingly soluble in acetone. These are stable in dry atmosphere but decompose on long exposure to moist air and are hydrolysed when boiled with water or strong alkali solution; but cold water is without action [these dissolve slowly in HNO_3 (dil.) and immediately in HNO_3 (conc)]. On heating these decompose, generally with melting, but in a few cases decompose without melting. Benzylamine and *o*-toluidine compounds have sharp melting points. On heating with soda-lime the corresponding amines are liberated and condensed in the cooler parts of the tube. On heating alone these furnish white, grey, brown, or yellow sublimes which respond to the tests for $-\text{NH}_2$ and Cl groups. These compounds respond to the diazo test. Compounds with diamines are more stable than those with monoamines.

DISCUSSION

The co-ordination number of thorium in these compounds is four and chelate compounds are formed in case of diamines, which are perhaps responsible for their greater stability. Though maximum co-ordination number (8) for thorium is not attained, compounds are very stable, probably due to symmetrical structure. These compounds may be represented as $[\text{Th.4M}]\text{Cl}_4$ and $[\text{Th.2D}]\text{Cl}_4$, where M=a monoamine and D=a diamine molecule.

The authors' sincere thanks are due to the authorities of the Banaras Hindu University for providing necessary facilities.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
BANARAS HINDU UNIVERSITY,
VARANASI-5.

Received April 26, 1961.